

Analysis of shock response of sandwich composites

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Abstract:

Sandwich composites are being aggressively pursued as structural materials by various defense and commercial industries. These include navy, air force, and army, automotive and sporting industries to name a few. In the context of structural load bearing members and absorbing dynamic loads, foam core sandwich composites offer unique advantages over traditional composites. The cellular construction of the foam materials not only provides lightweight capability but also a deformation mechanism that allows efficient absorption of energy. Of particular interest in this study is to investigate the behavior of the foam materials and their sandwiches under high strain rate (HSR) loading which are very much prevalent in their actual applications.

1. Introduction

Structures in Navy applications are often subjected to high strain rates due to impact by hard objects, mine blast, projectile impact, collision, etc. Traditionally, cellular or metallic foams are used as core materials in the sandwich construction to absorb energy under such impact events. Use of foam core for example, will require first-hand knowledge of the effect of impact velocity and strain rate on the behavior of those materials. In order to improve the dynamic performance of sandwich structures a thorough understanding of foam behavior to high strain rate loading is essential for tailoring and using these materials effectively in such applications. Very limited knowledge, however, exists on the behavior of such materials to high strain rate loading. Previous studies [1–4] have investigated the response of a sandwich specimen in compression at both low and high strain rates. Such studies show that the dynamic behavior of a sandwich is indeed a function of the properties of the core material.

PVC foams are widely used as core materials in naval sandwich structures. The behavior of such foams at high strain rate loading has not yet been determined to the fullest extent. Most studies cited in the literatures were conducted on polymeric materials including styro-foams and polyurethane.

2. Experiment

2.1. Materials and fabrication

2.1.1 PVC cores

Four closed-cell PVC foam cores were used as the core material for the sandwich specimen. Three of the four cores are cross-linked foams of various densities 75, 130, and 300 kg/m³. The fourth core used in his study also had a density of 130 kg/m³ but a lighter degree of cross-linking, which will be referred to as linear. The foams were manufactured by DIAB and are labeled R75, H1 30, R300, and HD130, respectively.

The foams were delivered in the form of 12.7 mm thick panels. Mechanical properties of the foams as determined by DIAB using standard test methods are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 - Properties of PVC foam as specified by

Property	Unit	Grade			
		R75	H130	HD130	R300
Density	kg/m ³	75	130	130	300
Compressive strength	MPa	1.1	2.5	2.1	7.8
Compressive modulus	MPa	38	175	140	700
Tensile strength	MPa	2.0	4.2	3.2	9.3
Shear strength	MPa	0.9	2.0	1.6	4.8
Module	MPa	29	52	32	137

DIAB

2.1.2 Fabrication of sandwich panels

Sandwich panels were fabricated using PVC foams as core materials. Vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) process was used for manufacturing the sandwich panels. VARTM allowed simultaneous infusion of top and bottom face sheets as shown in Fig. 1. Three layers of dry plain weave S2-glass fiber preforms were placed on a flat aluminum plate to form the bottom face sheet. The core was then placed above the bottom face sheet and then three layers of the same glass fabric were put on top to build the top face sheet. After stacking, the assembly was vacuum bagged, and infusion lines were installed. Before infusion, the system was de-bulked for several hours. Vinyl

ester (Dow Derakane 411-350) resin manufactured by Dow Corning was used in the fabrication process. After completing infusion, the system was kept under vacuum until the panel was completely cured. The thickness of each face sheet was approximately 1.9 mm, while the core thickness was 12.7 mm.

Fig. 1. Schematic of VARTM process used for fabricating sandwich composites.

2.2. Test methods

PVC cores and sandwiches were subjected to quasi-static and HSR compressive loading in the thickness direction. Quasi-static compression tests were performed using an MTS servo-hydraulic testing machine. Compressive loads at strain rates of 300 s^{-1} and above were conducted using a split Hopkinson pressure bar (SHPB) apparatus. A regular SHPB setup consists of three merging steel bars: a striker, incident, and a transmission bar. Special challenges are presented when using a regular SHPB for sandwich composites or soft cores, such as foams. When testing these types of material a very weak transmitted pulse is obtained due to the high impedance mismatch between the bar material and soft foam specimen, therefore accurate measures of strain signal are not possible. Lately, other researchers have incorporated new techniques to study the response of low stiffness materials at high rates of compressive loading. These techniques include the use of low stiffness bars made from nylon and polycarbonate. In this study, a modified SHPB technique which consisted of an all polycarbonate system was used to evaluate the high strain rate response (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Modified SHPB apparatus and elevated temperature setup.

HSR tests were performed at room and elevated temperatures. Specimens tested at elevated temperatures were first placed in a furnace and heated to the desired temperature. A temperature

probe and thermocouples were used to monitor the temperature of the furnace and foam specimen (Fig. 2). After heating the samples to desired temperature, they were immediately placed in the SHPB setup for testing. During this time frame, it was found that the samples lost $2\text{--}3^\circ\text{C}$ in temperature before testing was completed. Therefore, specimens were heated correspondingly $3\text{--}4^\circ\text{C}$ higher than the desired temperature to account for any loss of temperature during the transportation of the specimen from the furnace to the SHPB apparatus for testing. Temperatures recorded in this study indicate the temperature of sample during the time of testing. Samples were tested at various strain rates, which were acquired by varying the beech pressure. Strain gages were mounted on both the incident and transmission bars. The voltage vs. time graph was obtained as output from the strain gages, and then converted to strain signals. The strain vs. time and stress vs. time are determined from the incident and transmission bar, respectively. The stress–strain curves were then produced from the strain and stress time history by eliminating the time axis. In order to achieve sub-ambient temperatures, specimens were first submerged in liquid nitrogen and sealed for 30 min as shown in Fig. 3. Afterwards, each specimen was removed from the liquid nitrogen (196°C) and immediately placed in the SHPB for testing. Sandwich and foam specimens were subjected to compressive loading in the thickness direction for all tests.

Fig. 3. Liquid Nitrogen setup for sub-ambient tests.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Response of PVC core materials

The quasi-static compression behavior of the cross-linked PVC cores are shown in Fig. 4. Three distinct phases can be identified from the stress–strain curves. Each core density portrayed an initial

elastic region up to initial failure, followed by a stress plateau, then a region of densification. The stress plateau in case of R300 foam is however, not of constant stress as seen with R75 and H130 categories. It is believed that stronger and smaller cell structures which are typical with higher density foam are responsible for such behavior. A similar compressive behavior was found by Gibson and Ashby in a study on polyurethane foams. Each of the three phases correlates to a specific failure mechanism that the foam undergoes during compression. For closed-cell foams, the linear region is controlled by the stretching of the cell faces. The stress plateau is associated with the collapse of cells. When the cells have completely collapsed, the cell walls touch and further strain the solid itself, giving the final region of rapidly increasing stress.

Fig. 4. Quasi-static compressive behaviors of PVC foam cores at room temperature.

The compressive response of the foams is related to its relative density, which is a ratio of the foam density to the density of the solid from which it is made. As the relative density increases the cell size decreases, which means more of the solid is contributing to the foam mechanical properties rather than the gas (usually air) within the cells. For this reason, as the density of the PVC foams increase, an increase of compressive strength is observed. A 73% increase in strength was observed when comparing R75 and H130, whereas, a 130% increase was achieved when comparing R75 and R300. A similar behavior was found by Brezny and Green in a study regarding the effect of cell size on the mechanical behavior of cellular carbon foams. They observed that the strut strength of the carbon foams was not constant but rather increased with smaller cell sizes which caused the compressive strength to increase inversely with cell size. Also as density of the PVC foam increased, the rapid densification occurs at a smaller strain which leads to a shortening of the stress plateau. Increase in stiffness is also observed with increasing density.

The stress–strain curves for H130 foams at higher rates of strain are illustrated in Fig. 5. In general, a slight increase of strength was observed at higher rates of strain. This increase was moderate with this particular density (H130), however, it was more

prominent with lower density (R75), and almost insignificant with higher density (R300) foams. The stiffness of the foams was not much affected by the increasing strain rate, especially at the higher densities. The highest core density also achieved the highest failure stress for the entire range of densities. If the area under the stress–strain curves is considered to be a measure of the energy absorbed by the foam, then energy absorption increased proportionally with strain rate for all three cases (R75, H130 and R300). As shown in Fig. 5, a large amount of the energy absorption occurs through the collapse of the cells which is represented by the stress plateau; relatively very small amount of energy is absorbed in the linear regime. An increase in strain and an elongation of the plateau was also observed with increasing strain rate for each foam density.

Fig. 5. H130 stress–strain curve at various strain rates.

The elongation of the stress plateau indicates an increase of collapsed cells with strain rate, which can be seen in Fig. 6. Cell collapse and densification bands were more pronounced in the lower density foams (R75 and H130). As the density increases to 300 ($\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$), a slight change in failure mode was observed. R300 specimen achieved a lesser degree of densification along with some shearing near the center of the specimen. The extent of damage increased as the strain rate increased.

Fig. 6. HSR compression of foam cores at various rates (a–c) R75, H130, and R300.

3.1.1 Temperature effects

The effect of temperature on the high strain rate response of H130 foam is illustrated in Fig. 7. All the specimens within a specific category were

tested at similar strain rates. Stress–strain curves are very similar to what has been seen earlier. Tests were also conducted at quasi-static loading, and it was observed that similar to quasi-static loading, as temperatures increased a decrease in strength occurred. Also foam stiffness reduced slightly as the temperature increased.

Fig. 7.HSR response of H130 core at various temperatures.

The response of R75 and R300 was almost identical to that of H130, except that at higher density the temperature effects both on strength and stiffness became more pronounced. This is reflected in the temperature sensitivity curves shown in Fig. 8. It is clearly seen that as the relative density increases, the sensitivity to temperature also increases. In case of higher density foam (R300, relative density, 0.208) degradation rate also seems to increase as one approaches to the T_g (85–95 °C) of the solid polymer.

Fig. 8. Temperature sensitivity of cores at HSR loading.

Although a similar trend was obtained at quasi-static and HSR loading, differences can be seen in the strength of the foams. For instance, when comparing the strength degradation of the R75 specimen within a particular strain regime, Table 2, the strength decreased with increased temperature for both quasi-static and HSR, but the strength degradation was more pronounced in the quasi-static regime than at higher rates of loading. This behavior was observed in all densities.

Table 2 - Strength degradation at quasi-static and high rates of strain (R75)

Temperature (°C)	Quasi-static strength degradation (%)	HSR_ (1400 s ⁻¹) strength degradation (%)
55–60	3.8	0
80	12.3	3.6
110	42.3	12.2

Table 3 shows the peak stress of R75 for a variety of temperatures at both quasi-static and a rate of 1400 s⁻¹. When comparing the effect of strain rate at a specific temperature, the strength of the foams increased as one moves from quasi-static to higher rates. For example, the peak stress of the R75 specimen increased by 48% at room temperature, and as temperature increases, this percentage increases to 129%. This phenomenon may be due to a combination of the presence of the gas within the closed cells at elevated temperatures, and the short time response during HSR loading. The compressibility of a gas in a closed-cell depend on temperature, therefore as temperature increases the pressure within the cell increases, hence giving an additional restoring force to the foam. Although the overall strength of the foam is decreasing, the gas within the cell is contributing some strength during the short duration of the load at HSR.

Table 3 - Temperature effects at quasi-static and high rates of strain (R75)

Temperature (°C)	Quasi-static peak stress (MPa)	HSR (1400 s ⁻¹) peak stress (MPa)	Strength increase (%)
RT	1.30	1.93	48
55-60	1.25	1.93	54
80	1.14	1.86	63
110	0.75	1.72	129

3.1.2 Effect of microstructures

Several specimens of H and HD category foams were subjected to quasi-static as well as high strain rate loading. As shown in Fig. 9, three phases of failure, which are typical of foams can be identified. The quasi-static compressive strength of HD was approximately 30% lower than the H grade of the same density. The H and HD achieved a compressive strength of 2.75 MPa and 2.11 MPa, respectively, which was well comparable to the compressive strength supplied by the manufacturer, and reported by Danielsson.

Fig. 9. Quasi-static compressions of H130 and HD130 Foams.

The high strain rate response of the H and HD grades were first evaluated at room temperature. Strain rates ranged from 700 to 1580 s^{-1} . Similar to quasi-static loading, the three phases of failure were still present, but a reversal of the foam performance was observed as shown in Fig. 10. It is noticed that throughout the entire range of the strain rate, HD grade is superior to that of H grade. Fig. 10 also indicates that the compressive strength of the HD is approximately 20% higher than that of H grade. The HD also has a slightly higher stiffness than the H. This change in the foam performance from quasi-static to high strain rate regime was surprising. According to Gibson and Ashby, the relative density, cell size, and cell shape all affect the mechanical properties of cellular foam. Since the foams considered in this study have the same relative density, the properties must be governed by its microstructure. When comparing the cell shape and cell size, the shape of the H130 cell is seen to be somewhat hexagonal, whereas the HD130 cell shape appears to be slightly irregular and elongated. The cells of HD also appear to be smaller and cell walls thicker. Since HD grade has smaller cells and thicker walls its strut (edges where cell walls meet) strength may be higher according to Brenzy and Green. Brenzy and Green explored the effect of cell size on the mechanical behavior of cellular materials, such as cellular ceramic. They found that the strut strength directly affects the mechanical behavior of cellular solids by doing simple crushing test. The crushing strength varied inversely with cell size and it is consistent with increasing strut strength with decreasing cell size.

Fig. 10. Stress-strain curves of H130 and HD130 foams at various strain rates and at room temperature.

Now if we compare the quasi-static and dynamic compression of a cell, the rate of loading is slower at quasi-static regimes, which means the cell does not instantly fail, but gradually collapses under increasing load. At dynamic or impact loads the compressive input force lasts for a short period of time, therefore the cells are more likely to be crushed rather than just simply collapsed. During this crushing phenomenon, we believe relatively stronger struts of HD foams offer more resistance to HSR loading than those of regular H foams. This is however, not the case during quasi-static loading. This also suggests that the strut strength has a significant role on the dynamic properties but relatively less effect on the quasi-static properties.

The effect of temperature on the high strain rate response ($1057 s^{-1}$) of the two PVC foams is illustrated in Fig. 11. The reduction in strength was more pronounced in the HD grade. This higher sensitivity of HD to elevated temperatures may be due to the foam being more viscoelastic because of its lighter degree of cross-linking. However, from room temperature to about 60 °C, the HD grade portrayed better compressive properties. As temperatures increased above 60 °C the foam properties reversed. This may be due to the fact that H grade being more cross-linked, the ability of the polymer to flow at higher temperatures was more difficult than a linear polymer (HD). The molecules of a polymer with a linear structure also possesses the ability to slide by each other upon heating which may have contributed to strength degradation.

Fig. 11. Temperature sensitivity of H and HD foam at $1057 s^{-1}$.

3.2 Sandwich response

Response of sandwich composites made from various core materials as mentioned earlier were also evaluated at quasi-static and HSR loading. The HSR tests were conducted in a split Hopkinson

pressure bar set up as shown in Fig. 2. Since the loading was in the thickness direction, the core mainly controlled the performance of the sandwich constructions. In all cases, the sandwich response was very similar to that of its core except that stiffness and strength were slightly higher because of the presence of the composite face sheets. In order to assess the integrity of sandwich structures at sub-ambient temperature, tests were also conducted under HSR loading by soaking specimens with liquid nitrogen. Response of two categories of sandwiches made from H and HD foams is shown in Fig. 12. Fig. 12 compares the sub-ambient response of the two sandwich specimens with the same core density but different degrees of cross-linking at similar strain rates. The HD, which is the linear core, surpasses the H grade by about 33%. A comparison with Fig. 10 shows that there is a moderate increase in strength for both categories at sub ambient temperature. It also indicated that the HD sandwich outperformed the H category by about 20% in the HSR regime at RT. Therefore, as temperature drops below room temperature, the difference between the two sandwich responses seems to increase. In another study, failure phenomena of foam at sub ambient temperature have been investigated. The failure was characterized by complete pulverization and expulsion of the core materials accompanied by separation of both face sheets.

Fig. 12. HSR response of H130 and HD130 sandwich composites.

4. Summary

The following are the summary from the above investigation:

1. With the increase in strain rate there is a moderate increase in the compressive strength of foam core materials.
2. At quasi-static and high strain rate regimes, increasing the temperature resulted in a degradation of strength and stiffness in all categories of foams. This degradation however, increased with the density of the core materials.
3. During HSR and elevated temperature tests some degree of recovery of volumes

of the strained samples were noticed. However, this recovery in volume did not translate to any increase in the residual strength of the cores.

4. Microstructures of the core materials were seen to have significant impact on their performances. Cross-linked (H) and linear (HD) foams tested under quasi-static and HSR loading demonstrated that their performances is in fact reversed when strain regime is changed. For example, at higher rates of strain HD outperformed H but the reverse was true at quasi-static loading.
5. With increasing temperature the degradation in strength of HD category foam was much more severe than that of H category. Degree of cross-linking in the base polymer was responsible for such behavior.
6. A moderate increase (with respect to room temperature) in HSR compressive strength of sandwich composites was observed at sub-ambient temperature. This increase in strength was higher for sandwiches with HD cores.
7. Although the increase in strength at sub-ambient temperature was moderate, the failure modes were noticeably different than those seen at room temperature. At sub-ambient temperature the failure was characterized by complete pulverization and expulsion of the core materials accompanied by the separation of face sheets. On the other hand at room temperature, the failure was dominated by delamination, core crushing, and partial core shear.

References:

- [1] Rosenberg JT, Ahrens TJ. ASME Paper No. 66-WAPT-7, American Society of Mechanical Engineers, NY, December 1966.
- [2] Lysne PC, Boade RR, Percival CM, Jones OE. Determination of release adiabats and recentered Hugoniot curves by shock reverberation techniques. *J Appl Phys* 1969;40:3786–93.
- [3] Dandekar DP, Beaulieu PA. Compressive and tensile strengths of glass reinforced polyester under shock wave propagation. In: Rajapakse YDS, Vinson JR, editors. High strain rate effects on polymers metal and ceramics matrix composites and other advanced materials, ASME Ad-vol. 48. New York: ASME; 1995. p. 63–70.
- [4] Dandekar DP, Boteler JM, Beaulieu PA. Elastic constants and delamination strength of a glass-fiber-reinforced polymer composite. *Comp Sci Tech* 1998;58:1397–403.